

1 **The transcriptional landscape of luminal A subtype breast cancer in humans: CORO2A.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50
8 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies
9 to define the transcriptional landscape of luminal A subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here
10 differential expression of CORO2A in luminal A breast cancer.
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1 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from
2 patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression
3 analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of luminal A subtype breast
4 cancer.

4 **Methods**

5 We utilized microarray datasets GSE45827 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene
6 expression analysis of luminal A subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based
7 computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE45827 was generated using
8 [HG-U133_Plus_2] Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array technology with $n=11$ normal breast
9 tissues (control) and $n=29$ luminal A subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis
10 was performed using GPL570. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array
11 [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=50$ primary breast
12 tumors of luminal A subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform
13 GPL6244. We used an R-based bioinformatic tool to perform whole transcriptome co-regulation studies
14 across multiple tissues (SEEK [6]). We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor
15 gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$
16 basal subtype patients, in $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in
17 $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (7).

13 **Rationale**

14 Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

15 **Results**

16 We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene
17 expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose
18 expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the luminal A subtype of human
19 breast cancer.

- 19 1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal A subtype

20 $n=11$ normal breast tissues (human)

21 $n=29$ primary tumors (breast; human; luminal A)

22 ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
23 227177_at	5.67E-10	-8.07	12.536492	-2.4404536	CORO2A	2317/29873	92.2

24 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and luminal A breast
25 tumors, we discovered differential expression of coronin 2A, encoded by CORO2A (located at 9q22.3) in
26 luminal A breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of CORO2A changed more than 92% of the
27 human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was
28 measured - in this case, 29,873 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased
quantity of CORO2A messenger RNA in luminal A subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of
CORO2A during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to luminal A breast cancer.

2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: luminal A subtype

$n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=50$ primary tumors (breast; human; luminal A)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8162744	6.40E-15	-9.402433	23.557771	-1.0737774	CORO2A	104/33297	99.7

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and luminal A breast tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CORO2A in luminal A breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The expression of CORO2A here changed more than 99% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CORO2A messenger RNA in luminal A subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CORO2A during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to luminal A breast cancer.

Thus, CORO2A is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the luminal A breast cancer subtype in humans.

In breast cancer as in any solid tumor, the function of the gene identified by whole transcriptome differential gene expression cannot be assumed to be the same as in non-transformed tissues. Thus, to identify gene products likely to interact with and/or be relevant to the differentially expressed genes function in the transformed tissue, we performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation studies using SEEK, an R-based computational tool that blindly and quantitatively identifies co-expression across the genome using a clustering method rather than integration-based differential gene expression methodology (6). This second whole transcriptome technology identified KIAA1244, ERBB3, BIK, C9ORF152 and DOPEY2 as the five genes across the transcriptome most closely co-regulated with CORO2A in the transformed human breast (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed human breast: CORO2A.

Finally, we evaluated the influence of CORO2A tumor expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer (**Figure 2**) (7).

Fig. 2: Relationship between CORO2A tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.
Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

Discussion

We describe here CORO2A as a component gene product of the luminal A subtype in human breast cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.

References

1. Parker, J.S., Mullins, M., Cheang, M.C., Leung, S., Voduc, D., Vickery, T., Davies, S., Fauron, C., He, X., Hu, Z. and Quackenbush, J.F., 2009. Supervised risk predictor of breast cancer based on intrinsic subtypes. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 27(8), p.1160.
2. Perou, C.M., Parker, J.S., Prat, A., Ellis, M.J. and Bernard, P.S., 2010. Clinical implementation of the intrinsic subtypes of breast cancer. *The lancet oncology*, 11(8), pp.718-719.
3. Prat, A., Parker, J.S., Fan, C. and Perou, C.M., 2012. PAM50 assay and the three-gene model for identifying the major and clinically relevant molecular subtypes of breast cancer. *Breast cancer research and treatment*, 135, pp.301-306.
4. Gruosso, T., Mieulet, V., Cardon, M., Bourachot, B., Kieffer, Y., Devun, F., Dubois, T., Dutreix, M., Vincent-Salomon, A., Miller, K.M. and Mehta-Grigoriou, F., 2016. Chronic oxidative stress promotes H2 AX protein degradation and enhances chemosensitivity in breast cancer patients. *EMBO molecular medicine*, 8(5), pp.527-549.
5. Romero-Cordoba, S.L., Salido-Guadarrama, I., Rebollar-Vega, R., Bautista-Piña, V., Dominguez-Reyes, C., Tenorio-Torres, A., Villegas-Carlos, F., Fernández López, J.C., Uribe-Figueroa, L., Alfaro-Ruiz, L. and Hidalgo-Miranda, A., 2021. Comprehensive omic characterization of breast cancer in Mexican-Hispanic women. *Nature communications*, 12(1), pp.1-19.
6. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S., Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.
7. Györfy, B., 2021. Survival analysis across the entire transcriptome identifies biomarkers with the highest prognostic power in breast cancer. *Computational and structural biotechnology journal*, 19, pp.4101-4109.